

BALANCING THE SCALES: WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND JOB COMMITMENT AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the extent of work-life balance (WLB) and the level of job commitment among public school teachers in the Division of Bais City, and their relationship with profile variables, including age, sex, civil status, and length of service. Using a descriptive-correlational design, 190 randomly selected teachers from clusters 6, 7, and 8 participated in the study. A validated questionnaire served as the primary research instrument. Data were analyzed using mean, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, and chi-square test. Findings revealed that teachers generally experienced a balanced work-life condition in areas such as satisfaction with family and self-life, awareness, workplace flexibility, and self-appreciation, although role overload remained a challenge. They also demonstrated high levels of affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Results further indicated a significant relationship between WLB and job commitment, with sex emerging as the only variable significantly associated with WLB. In general, the findings highlight that a well-maintained WLB strengthens teachers' commitment to their profession by supporting their emotional attachment, sense of obligation, and willingness to remain in service. This underscores the need for fair workload distribution, gender-responsive policies, and a supportive school environment to sustain teacher motivation, enhance well-being, and promote long-term retention in the public school system.

Keywords: *Affective Commitment, Job Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Normative Commitment, Public School Teachers, Role Overload, Work-life Balance*

INTRODUCTION

A growing body of literature shows that balancing personal and professional responsibilities has emerged as a major concern worldwide, particularly for those working in high-pressure sectors such as education. Recent studies point to a strong connection between work engagement and an individual's ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance (WLB). Wood *et al.* (2020) note that when organizations offer meaningful support, employees tend to feel more fulfilled and energized in their roles. This balance does more than strengthen their dedication to their work; it also contributes significantly to their overall sense of well-being. Gragnano *et al.* (2020) also mentioned that maintaining harmony across work-family and work-health dimensions is vital for long-term sustainability. Many countries face challenges relevant to workload pressures and low job satisfaction, which affect employees' motivation towards work. Job commitment is deeply influenced by organizational fairness, support, and opportunities for growth, all of which drive engagement and retention. Adamu Mafindi (2024) highlights key WLB challenges, such as excessive workload, financial stress, and lack of flexibility. Long hours and low salaries force teachers to seek extra income, leading to burnout and reduced commitment, underscoring the need to improve WLB.

In the Philippines, public school teachers face distinct challenges in achieving work-life balance. Their responsibilities often extend beyond teaching to include administrative duties, compounded by scarce resources and limited organizational support (Aquino *et al.*, 2023). These difficulties contribute to stress, burnout, and reduced job satisfaction, which negatively impact job commitment (Aruldoss *et al.*, 2021). These concerns echo the priorities outlined in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, especially SDG 3 on promoting well-being and SDG 8 on ensuring decent and productive work. When teachers are supported in maintaining a healthy balance between their professional responsibilities and personal lives, the benefits extend beyond individual wellness. Such support contributes to more stable, humane, and sustainable work environments conditions that ultimately strengthen the overall quality of education.

Few studies show that WLB significantly affects job satisfaction, motivation, and employees' well-being, all of which enhance workplace efficiency (Allen *et al.*, 2021; Gragnano *et al.*, 2020). Whenever employees are satisfied and motivated, they will be more efficient and devoted to their work, and are more likely to become stress-free. Similarly, job commitment is tied to organizational success, stress management, and employee retention, as committed workers are more likely to excel and stay in their chosen fields (Abdulaziz *et al.*, 2022; Munda & Gache, 2024). Despite the vital role educators play in the nation's education system, research on how WLB impacts their job commitment remains limited (Munda & Gache, 2024). Existing studies tend to focus on other industries or contexts, leaving the unique struggles of Filipino educators underexplored. This gap is especially noticeable in the Philippine public school system, where the relationship between teachers' WLB and their level of commitment to the profession has not been examined in depth. Although many educators report feeling overwhelmed by the demands of their roles, research has yet to fully capture how these

pressures shape their dedication and long-term engagement with their work, especially in the Bais City Division, stressing the need for focused studies on Filipino educators.

Grounded in an in-depth understanding of the local educational landscape and the firsthand challenges faced by public school teachers, the researcher aimed to examine this critical issue. The study aspired to enhance the well-being of teachers by identifying actionable strategies to promote WLB and reinforce job commitment. By addressing this overlooked area, the research intended to provide valuable insights to guide policies and practices, creating a more supportive and sustainable work environment for educators.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the extent of work-life balance (WLB) and job commitment of public-school teachers.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the public-school teachers' work-life balance in the following aspects:
 - 1.1 satisfaction with family and self-life;
 - 1.2 role overload;
 - 1.3 awareness towards work-life balance;
 - 1.4 job satisfaction and flexible environment; and
 - 1.5 self-appreciation of work?
2. What is the level of public-school teachers' job commitment in terms of the following aspects:
 - 2.1 affective;
 - 2.2 continuance and
 - 2.3 normative?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the public-school teachers' WLB and their level of job commitment?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the public-school teachers (age, sex, civil status, and length in service) and the extent of WLB?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between the public-school teachers' WLB of and their level of job commitment.

H₀2: There is no significant relationship between the profile of public-school teachers (age, sex, civil status, and length of service) and the extent of WLB.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research utilized a descriptive-correlational design. It is descriptive because it identified (a) the extent of public-school teachers' work-life balance in the following aspects: satisfaction with family and self-life, role overload, awareness towards work-life balance, job satisfaction, and flexible environment; and self-appreciation of work, and (b) the level of public-school teachers' job commitment in terms of: affective, continuance, and normative. On the other hand, it is also correlational because the aforementioned variables were correlated.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Bais City, Negros Oriental, Philippines, which comprises fifty-eight (58) public schools under the supervision of the Department of Education - Schools Division of Bais City. These schools include thirty-one (31) public elementary schools, ten (10) public integrated schools, and seventeen (17) public secondary schools, along with three (3) private schools operating within the city. The study specifically focused on public school teachers assigned to Clusters 6, 7, and 8, which represent varied school contexts and learning environments within the division.

Bais City continues to advance its educational landscape, with public schools serving diverse communities across both urban and rural areas. These schools play a crucial role in providing equitable access to quality education and in promoting holistic learner development. Within this context, examining the work-life balance and job commitment of public-school teachers is particularly significant, as teachers serve as key agents in nurturing student achievement and sustaining school performance.

The Schools Division of Bais City encompasses elementary, secondary, and specialized institutions, all operating under the policies and standards of the DepEd. The division is guided by initiatives that emphasize teacher welfare, professional growth, and the continuous improvement of instructional quality. Schools within the division also engage in active collaboration with parents, local government units, and community stakeholders to cultivate a supportive learning environment. Moreover, several institutions have begun integrating innovative teaching strategies and educational technologies to enhance pedagogical practices and improve learner outcomes.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study are the 190 randomly selected public-school teachers from a total population of 332 in the Bais City Division, specifically teachers from Clusters 6, 7, and 8. Random sampling was employed to ensure that every public-school teacher in these clusters had an equal chance of being included in the study. This method reduced selection bias and strengthened the representativeness of the sample, thereby allowing

for more accurate and generalizable insights into the work-life balance and job commitment of public-school teachers.

The table below shows the distribution of respondents:

Name of School	Population	Sample
Bais City National High School	146	83
Bais City National Science High School	19	11
Cambuilao Elementary School	9	5
Cipriano Alcala Memorial Integrated School	15	9
Dawis Elementary School	11	6
Manuel L. Teves Memorial High School	11	6
Okiot National High School	17	10
Okiot Elementary School	22	13
Olympia Island Integrated School	19	11
Pilot Elementary School	63	36
Total	332	190

Statistical Tools

The tools used by the researcher in analyzing the data were the following:

Mean. This was used in getting the extent of the public-school teachers' WLB and job commitment.

Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient. This was utilized to identify the degree of relationship between the public school teachers' (a) extent of WLB and level of job commitment, and (b) profile in terms of age and length of service, and the extent of their WLB. This tool was used since one of the variables was measured on an ordinal scale.

Chi-square. This was used to identify the relationship between the profile of the public-school teachers in terms of sex and civil status and the extent of their WLB. This tool was utilized since sex is a nominal scale.

For positive indicators, the following interpretations were applied by the researcher to describe the extent of the public-school teachers' WLB.

Rating	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of WLB (Positive Indicators)	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Well-Balanced	The feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 81%-100% of the time.
4	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	Mostly Balanced	The feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 61%-80% of the time.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Slightly Agree	Partially Balanced	The feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 41%-60% of the time.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Barely Balanced	The feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 21%-40% of the time.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Not Balanced	The feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 1%-20% of the time.

As for the negative indicators, the following interpretations were used:

Rating	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of WLB (Negative Indicators)	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Not Balanced	The negative feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 81%–100% of the time.
4	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	Barely Balanced	The negative feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 61%–80% of the time.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Slightly Agree	Partially Balanced	The negative feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 41%–60% of the time.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Mostly Balanced	The negative feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 21%–40% of the time.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Well-Balanced	

The negative feeling or behavior is experienced by teachers 1%–20% of the time.

As to the level of job commitment, the following descriptions were utilized:

Rating	Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Commitment	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21 5.00	– Strongly Agree	Exceptional Commitment	The level of commitment of the respondents is 81%-100% of the time
4	3.41 4.20	- Agree	High Commitment	The level of commitment of the respondents is 61%-80% of the time
3	2.61 3.40	– Slightly Agree	Moderate Commitment	The level of commitment of the respondents is 41%-60% of the time
2	1.81 2.60	– Disagree	Basic Commitment	The level of commitment of the respondents is 21%-40% of the time
1	1.00 1.80	– Strongly Disagree	Minimal Commitment	The level of commitment of the respondents is 1%-20% of the time

Research Instruments

The researcher utilized a questionnaire as the primary data-gathering instrument for this study to obtain concrete and reliable results. This tool was deemed most appropriate, given that the study employed a descriptive-correlational design and a quantitative approach, which required the collection of numerical data to generate an accurate assessment.

The questionnaire utilized in this study is self-made and specifically designed to address the research objectives concerning work-life balance and job commitment among public school teachers. It is composed of three parts. The first part is a disclosure statement and the second part is the checklist for the respondents' demographic profile in terms of age, sex, civil status, and length of service. The third and fourth parts of the questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to provide an assessment of the work-life balance and job commitment of the public-school teachers.

For validation purposes, the researcher presented the questionnaires to three experts in the field in addition to the panel members who first evaluated the entire research proposal. These experts assessed the accuracy of the instrument based on grammar, format, alignment of questions, construct, and criterion. The researcher then adopted and integrated all the corrections and suggestions of the panel members and validators for more clarity and definiteness.

To establish reliability, a pilot test was conducted on 30 randomly selected public school teachers in Bais City Division. These teachers were not part of the main respondents of the study. The items were evaluated using Cronbach's alpha. The reliability coefficients for the variables related to work-life balance were as follows: Satisfaction with family and self-life = 0.939; Role overload = 0.832; Awareness towards work-life balance = 0.715; Job satisfaction and flexible environment = 0.784; and Self-appreciation of work = 0.839. For the variables related to job commitment, the results were: Affective commitment = 0.898; Continuance commitment = 0.825; and Normative commitment = 0.882. Since all coefficients were greater than 0.70, the items for each variable were deemed reliable.

Data Gathering Procedures and Analysis

After the design hearing, the researcher incorporated all the panel members' corrections and recommendations. With the approval of the dean of Foundation University's graduate school, a request letter to carry out the study was forwarded to the superintendent of the Schools Division of Bais City. The signed and approved letter of intent was presented to the different school administrators within the scope of the study. During the distribution, the researcher thoroughly explained in writing the purpose and significance of the investigation. Retrieval of the questionnaires was made after the respondents had completed the survey.

All data were processed using Microsoft Excel and online calculators for analysis and interpretation.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study mainly focused on examining the work-life balance and job commitment of public-school teachers of Bais City Division. Specifically, it measured the extent of work-life balance in terms of satisfaction with family and self-life, role overload, awareness towards work-life balance, job satisfaction in a flexible environment, and self-appreciation of work. Additionally, it evaluated the level of job commitment, which is categorized into affective, continuance, and normative commitment.

This study is limited to the perceptions and self-reported experiences of public-school teachers in the Bais City Division during the specified period of data collection. It does not include teachers outside the public-school sector nor consider external factors beyond the predefined variables of interest, such as socio-economic influences or policy changes.

The study also does not account for longitudinal data, meaning it does not assess changes in work-life balance and job commitment over an extended period. Moreover, the results are constrained by the subjective nature of self-reported data, which rely heavily on the respondents' personal perceptions, honesty, and self-awareness. Since participants may interpret questions differently or respond in ways they believe are socially acceptable, the findings may be influenced by social desirability bias or selective memory. Such limitations could lead to either an overestimation or an underestimation of their actual experiences and attitudes.

Furthermore, self-reported measures cannot fully capture the complex dynamics between professional and personal domains, as these experiences may vary depending on situational or contextual factors not reflected in the survey responses. Additionally, while the study explored challenges in balancing professional and personal responsibilities, it does not establish causal relationships, focusing only on descriptive analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1.1. Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public-School Teachers in Terms of Satisfaction with Family and Self-Life (n=190)

I encountered the following situations:	\bar{x}	VD	EoWLB
1. I feel satisfied especially when balancing personal needs and work responsibilities.	4.11	A	MB
2. I feel satisfied when I am able to spend quality time with my family despite my busy work schedule.	4.06	A	MB
3. I am working on balancing family needs and work demands to enhance my overall satisfaction and well-being	4.03	A	MB
4. I find happiness and fulfillment in taking care of my family while maintaining my professional commitments.	4.01	A	MB
5. I am feeling more content and better equipped to manage both family and work life if given enough time for self-care.	3.98	A	MB
Composite	4.04	A	MB

Table 1.1. presents the extent of public-school teachers' work-life balance in terms of satisfaction with family and self-life, yielding a composite mean of 4.04. This mean is interpreted as mostly balanced, indicating that teachers generally maintain a positive equilibrium between work and personal life. This balance is supported by consistently high mean scores across all indicators, particularly in areas related to family satisfaction and self-fulfillment. Specifically, they reported high satisfaction in balancing personal needs with work duties ($\bar{x} = 4.11$), spending quality time with family ($\bar{x} = 4.06$), and maintaining personal well-being ($\bar{x} = 3.98$).

Table 1.2. Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public-School Teachers in Terms of Role Overload (n=190)

I encountered the following situations:	\bar{x}	VD	EoWLB
1. I find it challenging to meet all my work and family obligations simultaneously.	4.16	A	BB
2. I feel emotionally exhausted especially when juggling multiple roles.	4.05	A	BB
3. I feel significant pressure to meet high expectations in both my professional and personal roles, creating a sense of role overload.	4.03	A	BB

4. I have difficulty in maintaining a sense of balance with the increasing demands of my job and family life.	3.88	A	BB
5. I don't feel capable of managing the numerous responsibilities I have at work and at home.	3.85	A	BB
Composite	3.99	A	BB

Table 1.2 presents the extent of public-school teachers' WLB in the aspect of role overload, yielding a composite mean of 3.99, which corresponds to the category barely balanced. It is important to consider that the indicators in this scale are negatively phrased; thus, higher mean scores reflect greater strain and challenges in managing work and personal responsibilities. Although the verbal descriptions indicate agreement, the overall interpretation of "barely balanced" highlights that teachers are experiencing noticeable difficulty in maintaining balance across their multiple roles. This strain is most evident in the teachers' difficulty in meeting work and family obligations simultaneously (\bar{x} = 4.16), followed closely by feelings of emotional exhaustion while juggling multiple responsibilities (\bar{x} = 4.05).

Table 1.3. Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public-School Teachers in Terms of Awareness towards Work-Life Balance (n=190)

I encountered the following situations:	\bar{x}	VD	EoWLB
1. I always try to prioritize my responsibilities to achieve a healthy balance between family and work.	4.47	SA	WB
2. I recognize that poor work-life balance affects my overall well-being and performance.	4.42	SA	WB
3. I understand that setting boundaries between work and personal life can improve my mental health.	4.42	SA	WB
4. I am mindful of the need to allocate time for self-care to maintain balance and focus in both roles.	4.42	SA	WB
5. I am aware of the importance of maintaining a balance between my work and personal life.	4.40	SA	WB
Composite	4.43	SA	WB

Table 1.3 presents the extent of work-life balance among public school teachers in terms of awareness towards work-life balance with a high composite mean of 4.43, interpreted as well-balanced. This indicates that the teachers are highly aware and conscious of managing both their work and personal lives. The highest-rated indicators include setting clear priorities (\bar{x} = 4.47), recognizing the negative consequences of imbalance (\bar{x} = 4.42), and practicing self-care (\bar{x} = 4.42).

Table 1.4. Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public-School Teachers in Terms of Job Satisfaction and Flexible Environment (n=190)

I encountered the following situations:	\bar{x}	VD	EoWLB
1. I can perform better and feel stress-free when I have a supportive and flexible work environment.	4.41	SA	WB
2. I value having the freedom to adjust my work schedule to accommodate my family needs.	4.27	SA	WB
3. I experience higher job satisfaction and improved well-being when my workplace offers flexibility.	4.27	SA	WB
4. I can maintain a sense of balance between my career and personal life whenever I have a flexible work environment.	4.24	SA	WB
5. I feel satisfied with my job when I can effectively balance my personal and professional responsibilities.	4.22	SA	WB
Composite	4.28	SA	WB

Table 1.4 presents the extent of work-life balance among public school teachers in terms of job satisfaction and flexible environment, with a composite mean of 4.28, interpreted as well-balanced. This indicates that teachers generally experienced a well-balanced work life in relation to supportive work conditions and the presence of flexibility in their roles. Among the indicators, teachers expressed the highest agreement with performing better in a supportive and flexible environment ($\bar{x} = 4.41$), followed by valuing the ability to adjust schedules for family needs ($\bar{x} = 4.27$).

Table 1.5. Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public-School Teachers in Terms of Self-Appreciation of Work (n=190)

I encountered the following situations:	\bar{x}	VD	EoWLB
1. I appreciate the opportunity to support students and make a positive impact through my role.	4.44	SA	WB
2. I feel proud of my accomplishments and the contributions I make in my work.	4.29	SA	WB
3. I find satisfaction in knowing that my dedication to my responsibility's benefits both my family and workplace.	4.29	SA	WB
4. I feel more confident and motivated when my accomplishments are acknowledged.	4.28	SA	WB
5. I recognize my efforts at work and value the progress I've achieved in my career.	4.24	SA	WB
Composite	4.31	SA	WB

Table 1.5 presents the extent of work-life balance among public school teachers in terms of self-appreciation of work, with a composite mean of 4.31, interpreted as well-balanced. This indicates that teachers highly value and recognize the significance of their professional contributions. This indicates that teachers highly value and recognize the significance of their professional contributions. The highest-rated indicator was valuing their impact on students ($\bar{x} = 4.44$), followed by feeling proud of their accomplishments

and finding satisfaction in knowing that their dedication benefits both their family and workplace ($\bar{x} = 4.29$).

Table 2.1. Level of Job Commitment of Public-School Teachers in the Affective Aspect (n=190)

I encountered the following situations:	\bar{x}	VD	LoC
1. I feel a sense of pride in being a member of this school community.	4.11	A	HC
2. I enjoy working with my colleagues and students, which makes me excited about my job.	3.99	A	HC
3. I feel a strong sense of belonging to this school.	3.97	A	HC
4. I feel emotionally connected to my school and its mission.	3.88	A	HC
5. I would feel a deep sense of loss if I were to leave this school.	3.79	A	HC
Composite	3.95	A	HC

Table 2.1 presents the level of job commitment among public school teachers in terms of the affective aspect, with a composite mean of 3.95. This indicates that the teachers demonstrated a high level of emotional attachment and identification with their school. Teachers reported feeling proud to be part of their institution ($\bar{x} = 4.11$) and enjoying their work ($\bar{x} = 3.99$).

Table 2.2. Level of Job Commitment of Public-School Teachers in the Continuance Aspect (n=190)

I encountered the following situations:	\bar{x}	VD	LoC
1. I feel that staying with my school is a matter of necessity as much as desire	3.91	A	HC
2. I have invested a significant amount of time and effort in my career at this school, so I cannot easily leave	3.87	A	HC
3. The benefits I receive from working at this school, such as job security and retirement, make it hard for me to consider leaving.	3.82	A	HC
4. I find it very difficult to leave my school right now, even if I wanted to.	3.77	A	HC
5. I am not afraid of what might happen if I quit my job without securing another one first	3.34	SA	MC
Composite	3.74	A	HC

Table 2.2 shows the level of job commitment among public school teachers in terms of the continuance aspect, with a composite mean of 3.74. This indicates a high level of commitment based on practical and personal factors. These include job security, accumulated benefits, and the perceived costs of leaving their current position. Teachers reported staying in their school as a matter of necessity as much as desire ($\bar{x} = 3.91$),

suggesting that their retention is influenced by factors such as job security, benefits, and the cost of leaving.

Table 2.3. Level of Job Commitment of Public-School Teachers in the Normative Aspect (n=190)

I encountered the following situations:	\bar{x}	VD	LoC
1. I believe it is important to stay and honor my commitment to the school community.	4.07	A	HC
2. I believe that continuing to work here is the right thing to do, as I have a moral obligation to support my students and colleagues.	4.06	A	HC
3. I believe that loyalty is important and therefore I feel a moral obligation to stay with my school	4.02	A	HC
4. I feel obligated to remain in my position at this school because of the support I've received from administrators and colleagues.	3.85	A	HC
5. I believe that moving from one school to another does not seem unethical to me	3.76	A	HC
Composite	3.95	A	HC

Table 2.3 presents the level of job commitment among public school teachers in terms of normative aspect, with a composite mean of 3.95. Among the items, the highest-rated statement, “*I believe it is important to stay and honor my commitment to the school community*” (4.07), stresses that teachers deeply value loyalty and view commitment as an essential part of their professional identity. Similarly, teachers express that continuing to work in their current school is both a moral duty toward students and colleagues (4.06) and a matter of professional loyalty (4.02).

Table 3. Analysis on the Relationship between the WLB of the Public-School Teachers and Their Level of Job Commitment (n=190)

Challenges and...	Job Commitment			
	Affective	Continuance	Normative	Overall
Satisfaction with Family and Self-Life	$r_s = 0.721$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.285$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.303$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.567$ $p < .001$ (significant)
Role Overload	$r_s = -0.345$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = -0.032$ $p = 0.659$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.065$ $p = 0.370$ (not significant)	$r_s = -0.241$ $p < .001$ (significant)
Awareness towards Work- Life Balance	$r_s = 0.464$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.088$ $p = 0.230$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.232$ $p = 0.001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.306$ $p < .001$ (significant)

Job Satisfaction and Flexible Environment	$r_s = 0.628$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.5207$ $p = 0.004$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.139$ $p = 0.055$ (not significant)	$r_s = 0.413$ $p < .001$ (significant)
Self-Appreciation of Work	$r_s = 0.696$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.277$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.250$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.534$ $p < .001$ (significant)
Overall	$r_s = 0.760$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.241$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.254$ $p < .001$ (significant)	$r_s = 0.561$ $p < .001$ (significant)

Note: Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation (r_s) at 0.05 Level of Significance

Table 3 presents the correlation between work-life balance dimensions and job commitment, with all results showing significant relationships ($p < .001$). The results of the correlation analysis reveal that work-life balance (WLB) significantly influences the job commitment of public-school teachers, with affective commitment showing the strongest associations across almost all dimensions. Satisfaction with family and self-life demonstrated a strong positive correlation with affective commitment ($r_s = 0.721$, $p < .001$) and a moderate relationship with both continuance and normative commitment.

Table 4. Relationship between the Public-School Teachers' Profile and the Extent of Their Work-Life Balance (n=190)

WLB and...	Computed	p-value	Decision	Remark
Age	$r_s = 0.058$	0.427	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant
Sex	$\chi^2 = 20.75$	<.001	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
	Note:			
	Male: $\bar{x} = 3.57$			
	Female: $\bar{x} = 3.96$			
Civil Status	$\chi^2 = 0.103$	0.950	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant
Length in Service	$r_s = 0.115$	0.114	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant

Note: Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation (r_s) and Chi-Square Test (χ^2) at 0.05 Level of Significance

Table 4 explores the relationship between teacher profiles and their perceived work-life balance (WLB). Among the variables examined (i.e., age, sex, civil status, and length of service), only sex emerged as statistically significant ($p < .001$), with female teachers reporting higher WLB. Age, civil status, and length of service showed no significant relationship, suggesting that organizational and psychological factors such as workplace flexibility, personal awareness, and self-appreciation are likely more uniform and influential across demographics than previously thought.

DISCUSSION

Work–Life Balance in Terms of Satisfaction with Family and Self-Life

The results indicate that teachers are able to manage both professional and personal domains effectively, reflecting a mostly harmonious work–life arrangement. The findings align with Clark’s (2000) Work/Family Border Theory, which highlights the role of flexible boundaries and supportive contexts in achieving balance. They also support Gragnano *et al.* (2020), who emphasized that satisfaction in family and personal domains is central to work–life equilibrium. Likewise, Aquino *et al.* (2023) observed that Filipino teachers who prioritize family and self-care tend to experience higher levels of overall satisfaction and emotional well-being. This underscores the importance of sustaining supportive school policies such as fair and manageable workloads, recognition of teachers’ personal and family needs, and the cultivation of an encouraging work environment to strengthen the positive integration of work and life.

Work-Life Balance in Terms of Role Overload

Results show that these consistently high scores across negatively framed statements suggest that teachers frequently face competing demands that stretch their capacity, leaving them fatigued, stressed, and with limited personal time. Overall, the findings indicate that while teachers attempt to fulfill both professional and familial duties, the burden of role overload significantly hinders their ability to achieve optimal work–life balance.

From a theoretical perspective, this finding reflects Clark’s (2000) Work/Family Border Theory, particularly the concept of *permeability*, which occurs when the boundaries between work and home are blurred, making it harder to maintain equilibrium. The results also resonate with Shabir and Gani (2020), who identified role overload as a major barrier to both balance and productivity. Similarly, Abdulaziz *et al.* (2022) reported that teachers burdened by excessive role expectations are more prone to burnout and disengagement, which compromises their well-being as well as their professional commitment.

This stresses the importance of interventions that can reduce overload, such as clearer role descriptions, time management support, and institutional policies that safeguard teachers’ personal and family time. By addressing these pressures, schools can help teachers preserve both their effectiveness in the classroom and their overall well-being.

Work-Life Balance in Terms of Awareness towards Work-Life Balance

The results suggest that teachers not only acknowledge the importance of balance but also actively cultivate strategies to sustain it. Such high awareness reflects a proactive mindset that enables them to anticipate challenges, protect personal well-being, and remain engaged in their professional roles.

These findings correspond with Clark's (2000) Work/Family Border Theory, particularly the concept of "border-crossers," where individuals consciously navigate and negotiate boundaries between work and home. Highly aware teachers are better able to regulate these boundaries, making adjustments when work demands threaten to spill into personal life. This awareness helps them establish intentional routines that protect personal time such as scheduling rest, limiting after-hours work, and engaging in family or leisure activities thereby preventing emotional fatigue and supporting recovery from work stress. The results also align with Allen *et al.* (2021), who emphasized that awareness fosters effective boundary management and reduces the risk of stress and burnout. Likewise, Gragnano *et al.* (2020) highlighted that holistic awareness across family, health, and work domains is essential for sustaining long-term well-being.

A high level of awareness provides a strong foundation for teachers to engage in positive coping strategies, such as time management, self-regulation, and seeking organizational support. This suggests that schools and administrators can build upon teachers' existing awareness by implementing institutional mechanisms such as reducing excessive non-teaching tasks, strengthening practices that support teachers' personal and family needs, and fostering a work culture characterized by open communication, empathy, and emotional support. These initiatives help teachers maintain productivity and motivation, while in the long term, they contribute to minimizing attrition risks, supporting healthier work-life routines, and sustaining a dedicated teaching workforce.

Work-Life Balance of the Public-School Teachers in Terms of Job Satisfaction and Flexible Environment

The results suggest that when institutions provide room for flexibility, teachers are more likely to manage competing demands effectively, leading to higher levels of satisfaction and overall well-being. This finding aligns with Clark's (2000) Work/Family Border Theory, which identifies flexibility as a crucial factor in managing the permeability of boundaries between work and family domains. Flexibility allows teachers to adjust their responsibilities without compromising role, thereby minimizing stress and conflict. Supporting this, Wood *et al.* (2020) and Zerhouni (2022) asserted that flexible environments not only foster job satisfaction but also strengthen organizational commitment, as employees feel valued and supported. Aruldoss *et al.* (2021) similarly emphasized that when employees are afforded flexibility, they can meet both personal and professional responsibilities more effectively, leading to improved morale, reduced turnover, and a healthier work climate.

The result reveals that cultivating supportive and flexible work environments is not merely an employee benefit but a strategic approach to sustaining teacher engagement and productivity. Flexible arrangements, such as manageable schedules, reduced administrative burdens, or alternative workload strategies, could mitigate the high levels of stress commonly associated with the teaching profession. In the future, promoting flexibility can help prevent burnout, increase job commitment, and enhance the quality of instruction delivered to students. This accentuates the need for policies that prioritize teacher well-being as a key component of educational sustainability.

Work-Life Balance Terms of Self-Appreciation of Work

The finding signifies that teachers demonstrate strong self-appreciation of their work, reflecting a deep sense of intrinsic motivation and pride in their professional contributions. These results align with Clark's (2000) Work/Family Border Theory, particularly the concept of a supportive environment, where recognition and internal validation of effort promote personal well-being and effective border management. This supports the findings of Bregenzer *et al.* (2022), who emphasized that self-appreciation serves as a crucial resource that enhances work-life balance (WLB) and engagement in the face of daily challenges. Similarly, Gragnano *et al.* (2020) posited that acknowledging the value and impact of one's work contributes significantly to balancing professional, family, and health responsibilities. This is further reinforced by Siagian *et al.* (2024), who noted that self-recognition of work quality positively links WLB with job satisfaction and is further strengthened by organizational support.

The finding suggests that teachers' strong self-appreciation not only sustains their motivation but also serves as a protective buffer against stress and burnout. A deep sense of pride and recognition of one's impact provides teachers with an internal reservoir of strength that helps them persevere in the face of challenges.

Job Commitment in Terms of Affective Aspect

The findings highlight that teachers not only value their professional roles but also feel a strong sense of belonging and fulfillment within their workplace. This aligns with Meyer and Allen's (1991) affective commitment dimension, which emphasizes that employees who are emotionally connected to their organizations are more motivated, engaged, and loyal. Koo *et al.* (2019) further support this by noting that job satisfaction supports stronger emotional bonds, reducing turnover and promoting retention. Affective commitment is particularly significant in educational contexts because it translates into greater organizational citizenship behaviors, higher work engagement, and a willingness to go beyond prescribed duties to support both students and colleagues.

The finding of the study emphasizes the importance of creating supportive and inclusive school cultures that nurture pride and enjoyment in teaching. School leaders and policymakers may therefore reinforce this dimension by adopting collaborative environments, recognizing teacher contributions, and providing opportunities for professional growth. By investing in the emotional well-being of teachers, schools can cultivate a stable and committed workforce that directly contributes to improved student outcomes and overall institutional success.

Job Commitment in Terms of Continuance Aspect

The finding is consistent with Meyer and Allen's (1991) concept of continuance commitment, wherein employees remain in an organization due to perceived personal or financial costs of leaving rather than emotional attachment. Aruldoss *et al.* (2021) noted that although continuance commitment supports workforce stability and reduces turnover,

it does not necessarily foster genuine engagement or long-term job satisfaction. Likewise, Khan *et al.* (2021) found that employees who stay primarily out of necessity are more prone to reduced job satisfaction and disengagement. In this study, the high continuance commitment among teachers indicates stability in the workforce but also suggests retention driven largely by practical constraints. This underscores the need for institutions to provide supportive environments, meaningful professional development, and positive workplace experiences so that teachers' commitment is shaped not only by the cost of leaving but also by authentic engagement and loyalty.

Job Commitment in Terms of Normative Aspect

The responses indicate that moral obligation and ethical responsibility are central factors influencing teachers' decision to stay. Slightly lower but still strong is their agreement that the support they receive from administrators and colleagues obligates them to remain in their positions (3.85), highlighting the role of reciprocity and institutional support in sustaining commitment. The lowest mean score was recorded for the statement "*I believe that moving from one school to another does not seem unethical to me*" (3.76), suggesting that while teachers recognize that mobility is not inherently unethical, their present sense of loyalty and moral attachment outweighs the desire to transfer.

This finding signifies that teachers are guided by a sense of moral conviction and perceived obligation to remain in their profession. This finding aligns with Meyer and Allen's (1991) framework, particularly the normative dimension, which posits that employees remain with an organization due to a perceived obligation rather than affective attachment or financial necessity. Mohd Rasdi and Tangaraja (2022) further emphasize that normative commitment nurtures organizational stability, cooperation, and loyalty, particularly in public institutions where collective responsibility is highly valued. In the Philippine context, this may also reflect cultural expectations, such as the values of *pakikisama* (harmony) and *utang na loob* (sense of indebtedness), which strengthen teachers' moral obligation to stay.

Relationship between the WLB of the Public-School Teachers and Their Level of Job Commitment

The results suggest that teachers who maintain harmony between personal and family life are more emotionally attached to their schools and feel a heightened sense of belonging, which enhances overall commitment. This supports the findings of Yusnita *et al.* (2022) and Quines and Arendain (2023), who emphasized the central role of family and personal well-being in strengthening teachers' emotional attachment to their work. It also aligns with Clark's (2000) concept of effective border management; wherein successful integration of work and family domains enhances commitment and engagement. Conversely, role overload was found to have a significant negative correlation with affective commitment ($r_s = -0.345, p < .001$), consistent with Shabir and Gani (2020), who noted that excessive demands increase stress and weaken emotional bonds. This reflects Clark's notion of high permeability between work and home, where blurred boundaries undermine commitment and satisfaction.

Meanwhile, job satisfaction and a flexible work environment, awareness towards work-life balance, and self-appreciation of work exhibited positive correlations with affective, continuance, and normative commitment. These results indicate that when teachers work in supportive and flexible conditions, recognize their contributions, and are conscious of balancing strategies, their emotional, rational, and moral ties to their institutions are strengthened. Such findings reinforce Meyer and Allen's (1991) Three-Component Model, which underscores affective, continuance, and normative commitment as complementary dimensions, while also echoing Clark's (2000) emphasis on flexible arrangements and supportive environments as key enablers of balance. Overall, the strong positive correlations between WLB and job commitment validate the theoretical integration, confirming that improved balance promotes stronger commitment across all dimensions, particularly by deepening affective connections while still influencing continuance and normative bonds.

In general, WLB demonstrated a very strong positive correlation with affective commitment ($r_s = 0.760$, $p < .001$) and a strong relationship with overall job commitment ($r_s = 0.561$, $p < .001$). These findings emphasize that fostering teachers' affective commitment relies heavily on creating supportive environments that promote personal satisfaction, flexibility, and recognition of their contributions.

Prior studies confirm that when teachers experience a healthy work-life balance, their emotional connection to the organization is strengthened, leading to higher affective commitment (Koo *et al.*, 2020; Ampofo, 2020). Quines and Arendain (2023) further emphasized that a balanced integration of work and personal life enhances teachers' dedication while reducing turnover intentions. Likewise, Yusnita *et al.* (2022) found that work-life balance serves as a direct predictor of job commitment, while Munda and Gache (2024) identified it as a determinant of employee loyalty and retention. These studies support the present results by showing that affective commitment thrives when organizational environments encourage satisfaction, recognize contributions, and provide flexibility that aligns work with personal life.

Indeed, schools should prioritize initiatives that ease role overload, such as redistributing workloads and reducing excessive non-teaching tasks, to prevent emotional disengagement. Abdulaziz *et al.* (2022) noted that work-life balance helps buffer the negative impact of excessive workload among teachers, while Shabir and Gani (2020) explained that role overload heightens stress and weakens commitment.

Moreover, policies that strengthen family-work integration and recognize teachers' achievements are likely to enhance their sense of pride and belonging, ultimately improving both retention and performance. This is consistent with Shi *et al.* (2020), who found that family-supportive supervisory behaviors increase satisfaction with family and self-life, and with Wood *et al.* (2020), who stated that the role of flexible work arrangements in enhancing job satisfaction and organizational commitment. While continuance and normative commitments are present, they are less influenced by work-life balance, suggesting that teachers' decision to stay is shaped more by emotional and personal fulfillment than by obligation or necessity (Loan, 2020; Khan *et al.*, 2021).

Relationship between the Public-School Teachers' Profile and the Extent of Their Work-Life Balance

While women reported higher levels of work–life balance, Torres et al. (2024) noted that they also tend to experience greater stress than men due to the dual pressures of professional duties and caregiving responsibilities. This indicates that female teachers may perceive balance not because demands are lighter, but because they employ adaptive coping strategies that enable them to manage both work and family roles effectively. This is consistent with the claims of Cabaraban and Borbon (2021) that women often demonstrate stronger resilience and coping mechanisms when handling multiple responsibilities.

This finding implies that higher perceived WLB among female teachers may reflect their capacity to maintain equilibrium despite substantial emotional and caregiving demands. This suggests that women may rely more on emotional regulation, time-management skills, and support networks to achieve balance, whereas men may experience challenges in navigating similar dual expectations.

Meanwhile, the absence of significant differences across other demographic variables implies that WLB is not solely shaped by individual characteristics. Rather, it points to the influence of institutional supports such as equitable workload distribution, administrative backing, flexible work arrangements, and a positive school culture. This aligns with Clark's (2000) Work/Family Border Theory, which emphasizes the importance of flexible boundaries and role permeability in maintaining balance. Ultimately, while demographic characteristics such as sex contribute to differences in perceived WLB, the results suggest that organizational and psychological factors play a more critical role in shaping teachers' work–life harmony.

Conclusions

The findings of this study affirm that public-school teachers in the Division of Bais City generally maintain a favorable level of WLB and exhibit a high degree of job commitment. Teachers show high awareness of maintaining personal and professional equilibrium and possess a healthy sense of self-appreciation; however, these internal resources are insufficient to offset the external and structural challenges they face. Heavy workloads and unclear role expectations remain the primary factors hindering consistent balance. The significant positive relationship between work–life balance and job commitment suggests that teachers who manage their roles well become more emotionally attached and dedicated to their profession. Although female teachers reported slightly higher balance, possibly due to coping strategies or support systems, the overall findings highlight that real improvement requires more than individual awareness. Meaningful change depends on systemic reforms, particularly reducing workload pressures and clarifying role expectations, so that teachers' internal strengths can translate into sustained well-being and professional commitment.

These findings stress the importance of a supportive and flexible work environment that promotes teachers' well-being and engagement. Strengthening WLB initiatives, including workload management, wellness programs, and gender-sensitive policies, can improve teachers' professional commitment, job satisfaction, and the quality of education. Achieving a healthier balance between professional responsibilities and personal well-being enables teachers to be more effective, resilient, and committed to sustaining educational excellence.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, several recommendations are proposed for key stakeholders. For school administrators, it is recommended that teaching loads be adjusted and non-teaching tasks such as excessive paperwork and redundant reporting be reduced to address role overload. The digitalization of teaching tools and reporting systems should be strengthened to streamline administrative processes, allowing teachers to focus more on instruction and student engagement. Additionally, schools are encouraged to institutionalize the Holistic Teachers' Wellness and Work–Life Balance Program by integrating it into the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Plan (AIP). Maintaining a supportive work culture that values open communication, empathy, and emotional support is also essential; this may be achieved through regular check-in meetings, an open-door policy for administrative guidance, and the establishment of mentorship or peer-support systems to strengthen collegial relationships.

For policymakers, particularly the Department of Education and Local Government Units, policy support and adequate resources should be provided for school-initiated teacher wellness programs, including family-inclusive activities, intramurals, and fitness initiatives. To further reduce role overload, schools may be guided to optimize the roles of existing administrative and support staff to offload non-teaching tasks, thereby enabling teachers to focus more on instruction and wellness-related activities. Local policies may also assist schools in integrating wellness programs and efficient staff utilization into their annual plans.

For teachers, it is recommended that they practice self-care by setting clear personal boundaries between work and home responsibilities and by actively participating in wellness activities offered by the school, such as health breaks, symposia, and fitness programs. Teachers are likewise encouraged to model positive work–life balance practices for their peers and students and to engage in peer support, collegial collaboration, and mentorship as means of sharing effective strategies for managing stress and responsibilities.

Finally, future researchers are encouraged to further investigate how school culture and leadership styles influence teachers' ability to sustain a healthy balance between work and life domains.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher first secured permission from the Foundation University Graduate School and obtained approval from the Ethics Committee to conduct the study. Ethical clearance and formal approval were also granted by the Schools Division of Bais City, allowing the researcher to gather data from selected public schools. The researcher strictly adhered to ethical standards to safeguard the dignity, rights, and welfare of the study participants. Prior to their inclusion in the study, the respondents were fully informed of the study's nature, objectives, and procedures, including their freedom to withdraw and the assurance of voluntary participation without coercion.

To ensure confidentiality and privacy, all responses were anonymized, and personal data were handled securely. The research instruments, administered as online questionnaires via Google Forms, were reviewed for clarity, relevance, and ethical compliance. Participants were assured that their responses would be used solely for academic purposes and that no identifying information would appear in the report. During data collection, access to the Google Form was restricted exclusively to the researcher to prevent unauthorized access or data manipulation. After the data gathering, all responses were securely stored and analyzed responsibly, maintaining the anonymity of participants and institutions. Upon completion of the study and after the required retention period, all electronic data were permanently deleted from secure storage to ensure that no participant information could be retrieved, following institutional data privacy and ethical research protocols.

The study was conducted in full compliance with Foundation University's ethical research standards, emphasizing respect, transparency, and integrity at every stage. Additionally, the researcher declared that OpenAI's ChatGPT was used as a tool to enhance the readability and organization of the manuscript. After using the tool, the researcher carefully reviewed, revised, and took full responsibility for the final content of the manuscript. The AI declaration is attached in Appendix A.

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